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Research Article

Formulation and Evaluation of Herbal Hair Serum from *Clitoria ternatea* Flower Extraction

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ABSTRACT

Cosmetics play a significant role in daily life, primarily for enhancing beauty and caring for the skin. Numerous commercial brands are available in a market for daily use. These products contain synthetic chemicals, which can lead to adverse effects. In recent times, there has been a growing preference for herbal cosmetics, as they are perceived to have fewer side effects and greater safety. Hair, being a crucial element of elegance and visual appeal is often the focus of various herbal products, including shampoos, oils, dyes, and hair serums. Hair serum serves as a cosmetic formulation aimed at mitigating hair loss, enhancing hair texture, and strengthening hair strands. The primary goal of this study is to formulate an herbal hair serum using *Clitoria ternatea* extract to stimulate hair growth. Additional components, including flaxseeds, fenugreek, aloe vera, and rose water, are incorporated into the serum's preparation. Three batches were prepared by varying the proportions of these ingredients. Each batch was evaluated for physical appearance, pH levels, homogeneity, viscosity and spreadability. All evaluated parameters met the established standards, indicating satisfactory quality. Current research has revealed that herbal formulations are effective in enhancing hair consistency.

INTRODUCTION

Human hair plays a crucial role in shaping an individual's personality and is integral to the human body. As hair is often regarded as a key component of personal beauty, it is essential to provide appropriate care for it. Hair is widely recognized as a symbol of beauty among humans, and the scalp serves as a critical factor in hair

growth. The scalp consists of soft tissue layers that envelop the cranium and the regions of the head where hair emerges. It contains numerous hair follicles and sebaceous glands³. A hair follicle is a tubular structure located in the epidermis, the outermost layer of the skin, where hair begins its growth at the base of the follicle. The hair root consists of protein cells and receives nourishment

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from adjacent blood vessels. The process of hair growth is regulated by a complex and intricately mechanism that is not completely understood. This process is cyclical, which involve the synthesis and elongation of the hair shaft, followed by eventual shedding. In humans, hair typically undergoes three distinct phases: anagen, catagen, and telogen¹. The presence of sebaceous glands, combined with the cyclical environmental changes, increases the susceptibility of the scalp to mycotic infections, including conditions such as excessive dandruff, tinea capitis, scalp psoriasis, scalp folliculitis, head lice, and even alopecia³, all of which can lead to hair loss. Activating hair follicles is crucial for stimulating hair growth and mitigating hair loss. Herbal remedies are widely favored by the public, primarily due to their reduced likelihood of adverse effects and their overall safety. In many instances, herbal cosmetics demonstrate superior performance compared to synthetic alternatives, attributed to their efficacy and lower incidence of side effects. Consumers often utilize these products to enhance their appearance and preserve a youthful, attractive aesthetic⁴. A wide array of hair care products is available in the marketplace to address various hair needs. Among these, serums stand out as cosmetic formulations characterized by a high concentration of active ingredients, designed to deliver intensive nourishment to the deeper layers of the skin while ensuring a non-greasy finish that is suitable for use on the skin².

Clitoria ternatea, commonly referred to as ‘Butterfly Pea’ has a long-standing history of use in Ayurvedic medicine, where different parts of the plant are employed to address various health concerns, including indigestion, constipation, arthritis, skin ailments, and liver and intestinal disorders⁶. This species is a vine indigenous to tropical and equatorial regions of Asia, thriving in moist, neutral soils with minimal maintenance requirements. Taxonomically, it belongs to the kingdom Plantae, phylum Tracheophyta, class Magnoliopsida, and the family Fabaceae (Leguminosae). It is known by several common names, including Asian Pigeon Wings, Butterfly Pea, Blue Pea, and Anchan in Thai. The flowers of *C. ternatea* are particularly notable for their anthocyanin content, a pigment also present in various other plants, flowers, and fruits that exhibit blue, red, or purple hues⁵.

Figure 1: *Clitoria ternatea*

Clitoria ternatea

MATERIALS AND METHOD:

Table 1: Herbal Ingredients

	Butterfly Pea	Aloe Vera	Flaxseeds	Fenugreek
Botanical name	<i>Clitoria ternatea</i>	<i>Aloe Barbadensis</i> Miller.	<i>Linum usitatissimum</i>	<i>Trigonella foenum-graceum</i>
Family	Fabaceae	Liliaceae	Linaceae	Leguminosae
Synonym	Asian Pigeon Wings, Butterfly Pea, Blue Pea.	Aloe, Musab bar, kumari.	Linseed, flaxseed	Methi, Methika, Alholva, Chandrika.

Biological source	Flowers	Leaves of various species of aloe-vera	Dried fully ripe seeds of <i>Linum usitatissimum</i> Linn.	Dried seeds to <i>Trigonella foenum-graecum</i> .
Chemical constituents	Alkaloids, tannins, glycosides and ternatin anthocyanins.	Anthraquinone glycoside, aloin, barbaloin, aloemodin.	Alpha-linoleic acid (ALA), omega-3 fatty acid, lignans, etc.	Vitamin B, alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, etc.
Uses	Indigestion, arthritis, skin diseases, and intestinal problems.	Make stronger hair, it provides antioxidant properties and also act an emollient.	Anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidants, hair growth stimulator.	Hair growth stimulant, antibacterial.

❖ Rose Water

Rose water is a mild astringent which may help to reduce oiliness and dandruff. It has anti-inflammatory properties, which may make it beneficial for certain scalp conditions, like psoriasis and eczema. Many women with curly hair swear by rose water's ability to calm down frizz and add shine.

Extraction Work:

The flowers were harvested from the garden, subsequently dried in a shaded environment, and processed into a coarse powder. A quantity of one hundred grams of the dried flowers are additionally dried in a hot air oven at a temperature of 50°C for a duration of 45 minutes, after which they were ground into a fine powder by hands. This dried powder was then macerated with 50% ethanol (1000 ml) for a period of six days, followed by filtration through cotton wool and muslin cloth. The resulting extract was further filtered and subjected to evaporation under reduced pressure. The crude extract was subsequently evaporated in a water bath for two hours. The final dried extract was stored in a refrigerator until required for use in the formulation of hair-growth products.

Figure 2: Extraction by Maceration

Preparation of Herbal Hair Serum:

Solution 1: -

In a beaker, 5 grams of flaxseeds are combined with 50 ml of distilled water, and the beaker is placed in a water bath for heating until a clear, slightly viscous gel is produced. The gel is then filtered through muslin cloth. Subsequently, the viscous gel is placed on a magnetic stirrer to ensure uniform mixing.

Solution 2: -

In a beaker, combine 1 gram of fenugreek seeds with 20 milliliters of distilled water and bring the mixture to a boil for duration of 5 minutes. Subsequently, filter the resulting solution.

Solution 3: -

In the beaker, add sufficient quantities of solutions 1 and 2 as indicated in the formulation table. Incorporate the *Clitoria ternatea* flower extract

into this mixture and maintain it on a magnetic stirrer to ensure complete solubility. Subsequently, add Aloe vera gel, sodium benzoate, and rose water. Finally, adjust the volume of the solution with distilled water.

Table 2: Formulation Table

Ingredients	S1	S2	S3
<i>Clitoria ternatea</i> Flower Extract	10%	10%	10%
Fenugreek seeds	3ml	4ml	5ml
Flaxseed	10ml	7ml	5ml
Aloe vera gel	1ml	3ml	4ml
Rose water	1ml	1ml	1ml
Sodium benzoate	0.02gm	0.02gm	0.02gm
Distilled Water	Q.S.	Q.S.	Q.S.

Figure 3: Serum Formulation

Evaluation

1. Organoleptic Properties.

The organoleptic properties were assessed through the observation of the texture, color, and fragrance of the developed cosmetic serum.

2. Homogeneity Test³

A clean and dried glass slide was coated with the herbal serum and subsequently covered with a glass cover slip. The sample was examined under light for its appearance. Additionally, the serum

was assessed visually for homogeneity, as well as the presence of aggregates or floccules.

3. pH Test^{3, 4}

The determination of pH will be conducted by using a digital pH meter. Prior to measurement, the pH meter was calibrated with buffer solutions of pH 4 and pH 7. Subsequently, the probe of the digital pH meter will be immersed in the serum formulation sample, and the corresponding pH value will be documented. It is essential for the formulation to exhibit an acidic pH, as the skin typically maintains an acidic pH range of approximately 4 to 6.

4. Viscosity⁴

The viscosity of serum is determined utilizing a Brookfield viscometer equipped with spindle number 61. A sample of 30 ml of hair serum is placed in a beaker, and the viscosity is assessed at different rotational speeds, specifically at 10, 20, 50, and 100 RPM.

5. Spreadability²

The assessment of spreadability was conducted using a parallel plate method, a standard technique for evaluating the spreadability of semisolid formulations. A sample of one gram of hair serum was placed between two horizontal plates, each measuring 20 cm by 20 cm, with the upper plate exerting a weight of 125 g. The diameter of the spread was recorded after duration of one minute. The calculation of spreadability was performed using the specified formula.

$$S = M \times L / T$$

Where, S= Spreadability, M= Weight in the pan (tied to the upper slide), L= Length moved by the glass slide, and T = Time (in sec) taken to separate the slides completely.

6. Skin Irritation Test⁴

To check the skin irritation, apply the serum to the skin and check for redness or itching after 2 hr.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Organoleptic Properties:

The physical appearance, odor and texture of the prepared herbal hair serum are visually tested.

Table 3: Results of Organoleptic Properties

Parameter	Batch S1	Batch S2	Batch S3
Color	Brownish blue	Brownish blue	Brownish blue
Odour	Rose like	Rose like	Rose like
Texture	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth

2. Homogeneity Test.

A visual assessment of the serum was conducted to evaluate its appearance and to identify any lumps, flocculates, or aggregates, thereby determining its homogeneity. The results indicated

that the prepared serum exhibited a satisfactory level of homogeneity.

3. pH Test.

A digital pocket pH meter was used to measure the pH level of the serum. The pH meter was immersed in the serum and monitored for several seconds until stable readings were displayed.

Table 4: Results of pH Analysis

Parameter	Batch S1	Batch S2	Batch S3
pH of Serum	5.5	6	6.6

Figure 4: pH Analysis

4. Viscosity

Viscosity of serum in Brookfield viscometer shows as follow:

Table 5: Results of Viscosity Analysis

RPM	10rpm	20rpm	50rpm	100rpm
S1	10.6	11.6	10.8	8.63
S2	17.2	13.4	11	9.70
S3	20	14.6	11.7	13.38

Figure 5: Viscosity Analysis

5. Spreadability

Table 6: Results of Spreadability Analysis

Parameter	S1	S2	S3
Spreadability	Good	Good	Good

Figure 6: Spreadability Analysis

6. Skin Irritation Test

The serum is applied to skin and kept for 2 hr to check any irritation and redness. After 2 hr no irritation or redness observed.

CONCLUSION

The formulation of the herbal hair serum was achieved through a systematic process of trial and

error. This serum is enriched with a diverse array of nutrients that contribute to the maintenance of healthy hair and scalp conditions. It incorporates natural ingredients that support both hair care and growth. *Clitoria ternatea* is notable for its anthocyanins, which enhance blood circulation to the scalp, thereby facilitating hair growth. Flaxseeds are abundant in omega-3 fatty acids, which provide nourishment to the scalp and hair, ensuring they remain hydrated and in optimal health. Fenugreek seeds are a rich source of proteins, nicotinic acid, and lecithin, all of which are beneficial for scalp nourishment and hair growth stimulation. Additionally, aloe vera serves as an exceptional natural conditioner, effectively locking in moisture and alleviating dryness, resulting in smooth and soft hair strands. The final product exhibits a brownish-blue hue, a smooth texture, and a fragrance reminiscent of roses. The serum's pH level ranges from 5.5 to 6.5, and the viscosity and spreadability of all batches were found to be within acceptable limits.

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Conflict Of Interest:

No Conflict of interest.

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